

PRESENTATION OF THE PROBLEM OF VOCABULARY DEVELOPMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE WRITINGS OF Y. ALTYSARIN, A. BAITURSYNOV

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Abstract. *This article writes about the History of question, development of vocabulary of junior schoolchildren.*

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If we look at the history of mankind from ancient times to the present day, we can say that language is, first of all, an indelible, immortal, constantly evolving phenomenon. Language is the basis of culture, the conditions for the formation of a nation. Through language, each person himself expresses his thoughts, opinions, contacts with the outside world. Proper use of the language depends on the vocabulary of a person and its rational use. The vocabulary of children is smart, eloquent and expressive. One of the main directions of the modern education system is the formation and development of such qualities among students. If the language of the students is rich, then he will easily master the history, culture and treasures of the nation, accumulated over the centuries. This is a prerequisite for the education of children of patriotism and the ability to prove their words in accordance with modern requirements, be creative, think creatively, be personalities.

As known, at present the vocabulary of elementary school students is growing rapidly. This happens not only from the impact on children of the family, the environment, the Internet, social networks, television, but also through the words used in the textbook. Modern textbooks of the new generation, based on the idea of developing training and education, are complex and deep in the structure and content of the texts. It is known that the material is not fully mastered, do not turn it into an active vocabulary until the texts and the words used in the cognitive, educational, scientific plan understood. Therefore, increasing the vocabulary of students is becoming one of the pressing problems of our time. Ultimately, the work on improving the vocabulary of primary school students solves several important problems: firstly, students enter into language communication and freely express their thoughts; secondly, they understand the language materials presented in the textbook; thirdly, the language culture is being improved, with the reasonable use of words; fourthly, the richness of the student's words is expanding; fifthly, creativity develops.

Language training is carried out from the day a child enters school. In the primary grades, the child is studied the phonetic phenomena of the language, lexical features, grammatical patterns. Here, the teacher faces two tasks in teaching the Kazakh language. One of them is teaching students the correct pronunciation and spelling of a word, the second is to reproduce vocabulary,

correctly combine words. Sh. Uakbaev noted that "Expanding the vocabulary of students, an exercise in the ability to use words in their place, learning interconnected sentences, mastering spelling rules, literate spelling is the main goal of the Kazakh language lessons taught in elementary grades", also states "The child's verbal fund does not develop, not immediately upon arrival at school. This is a very long, complex process. And if the student has a lot of vocabulary, then he has well-developed thinking," which is one of the ways to achieve these goals vocabulary of children [1.4-25].

A child who comes to school does not only know the phonetic, grammatical aspects of the language, but also knows the vocabulary of the language, the meaning of words, that is, vocabulary. According to scientists, the first children entering school have 3-7 thousand words in the vocabulary [2]. The development of the vocabulary fund of such children in the future is the main task of the teacher.

Therefore, the problem of reproduction of the vocabulary has never been left without attention of scientists who have contributed to the development of the methodology of teaching the Kazakh language.

Y. Altynsarin, A.Baitursynov, U. Shonanov, G. Begaliev, A.Saduakasov, S.Zhienbayev, R.Amirov, K.Bozhanova, S.Rahmetova, E. Uzakbayev, B. Kulmagambetova, B. Katembayeva, K.Akbayeva, K.Moldabek, G.Uayisova, A.Zhumabayeva, M.Yermekbayev and others teachers expressed their opinion on the increase in vocabulary of elementary school students, revealed many aspects.

In the elementary school, teaching the Kazakh language, expanding the vocabulary of elementary school students began in the late 19th century. Since that period, the Kazakh intelligentsia has contributed a lot in teaching the Kazakh language and laid the foundations for the methodology of teaching the Kazakh language.

The scientist who first took control of the textbook's creation – Y.Altynsarin. There are few of them: "Initial manual for teaching Kazakhs the Russian language", "Kyrgyz anthology", "Maktubat". He directed all his time to educate the child, improve knowledge, culture of the Kazakh people. When studying the language, Y.Altynsarin focused on the need for a systematic study of grammatical patterns and meanings of the word. "A Kazakh child cannot remember anything because of the different complexities of the rules, there are even times when a child does not understand absolutely anything," he said [3.224].

Y. Altynsarin sought to determine the volume of the student's dictionary during the period of competent disclosure. In the work "Initial manual for teaching Kazakhs the Russian language", students highlight the words that students should own in large groups, such as a noun, adjective, numeral, pronoun, dominant, supportive, verb, prefix (called terms that are currently in force). He gave a lexical minimum for improving the vocabulary of students. In total, the lexical minimum presented by the scientist contains about 1300 words.

Y. Altynsarin wrote the words given to the lexical minimum to students in vocabulary books, explained the meaning of some words through related words. Although the scientist's work was aimed at studying the Russian language for Kazakh children, this was the first work on increasing the vocabulary of students. In the learning process, language materials are studied, based on the educational scientist, on the principle of consistency, maintaining vocabulary books for children performed in enriching the students' vocabulary, ways of explaining the meaning of a

word through a synonym for words that are still used in the educational process. This indicates that the problem of improving the vocabulary of students began with Y. Altynsarin.

One of the founders of the Kazakh language teaching methodology is Akhmet Baitursynov. His works on the methodology of teaching the Kazakh language: "Which method is better?", "About the classification of sounds", "Stress (analysis; method)", "Stress-generalizing method", "Bayanshi", etc.

Despite the fact that the problem of increasing the vocabulary of students is not the subject of a special discussion, A. Baitursynuly conducts several works aimed at improving the vocabulary of students. In the course of the analysis of the scientist's works, it was noted that the students were asked to reproduce the wealth of the language in the following ways.

The first way to group words into topics. Here, on each topic, words were selected related to the daily life of students.

In the book "textbook", published in 1912, the words were divided into thematic groups, several were recorded for each group. He highlights the following topics:

1. relatives
2. Clothing;
3. toy games;
4. body parts
5. food and drink;
6. home equipment;
7. dishes;
8. domestic animals;
9. wild animals;
10. birds;
11. reptiles;
12. insects;
13. the name of the globe;
14. names of farmers;
15. numbers [4].

A. Baitursynuly set a goal to develop a system of cognition, thinking, vocabulary in children, highlighting words on topics. This approach is clearly manifested in the examples and assignments given in the textbooks in force in modern elementary school. When passing the letter "Y" in the modern textbook "ABC" children are given a grouping of words on topics, utensils: spoon, glass, wineskin; musical instruments: dombra, accordion, drinks: kymyran, juice.

The second, a way to transform the meaning of the word through the prefix to the root. A. Baitursynov carried out work here to transform the meaning of the word, first transmitting the root words of two sounds, and then adding affixes. For example, food, housing, housing, a hotel, etc. It is obvious that this approach is aimed at increasing the vocabulary of students not only by teaching reading and writing, but also by adding suffixes to root words, creating new words and explaining the meanings of created words. By adding the suffix "ak" to the root of the word "con", students not only understand that the meaning of the word is changing, but also learn to successfully use the word "conak" in a sentence.

Thirdly, a way to create another word by changing the sound of one word. The scientist explained to students with examples that you can create another word by changing only one sound

of words. Here, students learn not only the rules of spelling, spelling, but also the lexical meaning of words. This method is widely used today in the textbook "ABC" for primary school students, which compares words with the letters a-ə.

The scientist suggested ways to consolidate the words learned by students through exercises. Fulfilling the work "Testing" and "Instilling skills" proposed by scientists, it forms the ability of students to correctly use the learned or mastered words.

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